

**LEGAL PROBLEMS OF PROVISION OF ENVIRONMENTAL SAFETY
AND PREVENTING NEGATIVE CLIMATE CHANGES IN THE SPHERE
OF FERTILIZER PRODUCTION IN UKRAINE**

**PROBLEME JURIDICE ALE REGLEMENTĂRII SIGURANȚEI MEDIU-
LUI ȘI PREVENIRII SCHIMBĂRILOR CLIMATICE NEGATIVE ÎN
SFERA PRODUCȚIEI DE ÎNGRĂȘĂMINTE ÎN UCRAINA**

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Summary. *The content of this article discusses the issue of Legal Problems of Provision of Environmental Safety and Preventing Negative Climate Changes in the Sphere of Fertilizer Production in Ukraine.*

Keywords. *CO2 emissions, fertilizer production, greening of production, environmental safety, environmental legislation, EU Ecological Course, Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism.*

Introduction

The fertilizer production process emits CO₂ and other harmful chemicals into the air. This causes damage to the environment, violates the right of citizens to a safe and healthy environment, and inevitably leads to negative climate change. The EU's environmental policy and the creation of the Carbon border adjustment mechanism (CBAM), which came into force in early 2023, help to overcome negative climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions in the EU and around the world. At the same time, the main impact of this initiative is aimed at fertilizer exporters outside the EU to prevent carbon leakage. The introduction of such initiatives will have an impact on environmental safety in the production process and will also

help to level the playing field in the fertilizer market for European producers with exporters from third countries, including Ukraine.

The **purpose** of the article is to study the legal instruments implemented by the CBAM strategy; to determine its impact on third-country fertilizer exporters; to analyze the ways of its implementation in Ukrainian legislation; and to forecast the environmental and other consequences of its application for ensuring environmental safety in the field of fertilizer production in Ukraine. In order to achieve this goal, the following **tasks** have been set: to analyze the sources of European and national environmental and climate legislation, scientific approaches to the role of the CBAM in greening production, its impact on the EU fertilizer export market, and the implementation of EU climate legislation into the national legal system.

The **object** of the study is the social relations that arise in the field of ensuring the environmental safety of fertilizer production, as well as the implementation of EU climate change legislation on the example of the CBAM. The **subject** of the study is scientific, regulatory and legal sources of Ukrainian and EU law.

The **research methodology** is based on the following methods: analysis and synthesis (European climate legislation and the role of the CBAM in it, as well as Ukrainian legislation in the field of regulation of carbon dioxide emissions and environmental safety, analysis of scientific approaches to the role of the CBAM in greening production and development of legislation in the field of environmental safety in connection with European integration processes); statistical (determining the role of Ukraine and third-country fertilizer exporters in the EU fertilizer market, as well as assessing the possibilities of using biogas and biomethane as alternative energy sources for fertilizer production in the EU to develop legal regulation in this area); prognostic (proposals for improving the legal regulation of CO₂ emissions, as well as biogas and biomethane production, aimed at greening production), and others.

Assessment of the state of the literature. Problems of ensuring environmental safety in the field of economic activity, research on ways to implement EU legislation in the field of environmental safety and climate change prevention into Ukrainian environmental legislation have been the subject of research by V. I. Andreitsev (formation of environmental safety law), G. I. Balyuk (legal problems of ensuring environmental safety), L. O. Bondar (ensuring environmental safety in industry), M. V. Krasnova (the role of environmental assessment in ensuring the right to environ-

mental safety), Y.A. Krasnova (theoretical aspects of the development of environmental safety law), P.F. Kulinich (ensuring environmental safety in agriculture), N.R. Malysheva (current state and prospects for the development of environmental legislation under the influence of European integration processes), T.O. Tretiak (development of legislation on environmental impact assessment, realization of the right of citizens to environmental safety) and other scholars. At the same time, the mechanism for ensuring environmental safety of fertilizer production, as well as the specifics of implementing EU environmental legislation and legislation on the prevention of negative climate change on the example of the CBAM, have not been sufficiently studied in these works. The novelty and wide range of relations regulated by this initiative gives grounds to speak of the relevance of addressing these issues in the science of environmental law.

What is CBAM and what is the role of this initiative in ensuring environmental safety in fertilizer production?

In recent years, the EU has been pursuing an environmental policy aimed at transforming Europe into the world's first climate-neutral continent, in line with the Paris Agreement with its key element - the creation of a Green Deal. The main goal of this course is to transform the EU into a fair and prosperous society with a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy, where there are no net greenhouse gas emissions in 2050 and where economic growth is not linked to resource use. At the same time, it should be noted that the goals of this agreement will not be achieved by the EU's internal policies alone. This is due to the fact that the causes of climate change and biodiversity loss are global and not limited by national borders, and therefore the EU will use its means of influence on other states to increase the effectiveness of the implementation of this course [1].

As part of this course and the Fit 55 strategy, the CBAM is being implemented, which aims to address climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions in the EU and globally. This initiative is legislated in the Regulation (EU) 2021/0214 (COD) of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a border carbon adjustment mechanism and will be implemented in October 2023. Its goal is to tackle climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions in the EU and globally. The main sectors covered by this agreement include electricity, cement, fertilizers, iron and steel, aluminum, etc. At the same time, the main impact of this initiative is aimed at fertilizer exporters outside the EU to prevent carbon leakage and

ensure environmental safety of production in third countries. Among the fertilizers included in the list of fertilizers regulated by this mechanism are the following: nitric acid; sulphuric acids; ammonia, anhydrous or in aqueous solution; potassium nitrate; mineral or chemical nitrogen fertilizers; mineral or chemical fertilizers containing two or three fertilizing elements - nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium; other fertilizers; products of this group in tablets or similar forms or in packages with a gross weight of not more than 10 kg; mineral or chemical fertilizers containing two fertilizing elements - phosphorus and potassium. The main component of this initiative is the creation of new rules for imports into the EU of products manufactured by third countries with the creation of special permits. In the absence of such permits, the EU customs authorities should not allow the import of goods into their territory [1].

The permitting procedure involves monitoring, reporting and verification of activities related to carbon dioxide emissions. It should be noted that emissions are regulated in accordance with European standards, and therefore the main goal of such a system is to green production outside the EU. According to C. Mathieu, the CBA is the best chance to move from the unsustainable approach of implementing climate change initiatives only within the EU to applying mechanisms to influence exporters from third countries, requiring them to pay equivalent costs for carbon emissions and modernization of production [2, p. 6].

Thus, it can be concluded that the creation and implementation of the CBAM strategy will have a significant impact on the activities of fertilizer producers. These companies will need to modernize their facilities to ensure that they are able to export their products to the EU in order to obtain permission and export them to the EU. It can be stated that ensuring the environmental safety of the fertilizer production process will be a key factor in the further development of third-country exporters for the next decades.

Legal regulation of environmental safety in the production of fertilizers within the European Union: the impact of the CBAM on third-country fertilizer exporters to the EU.

The military aggression of the Russian Federation on the territory of our country has had a devastating impact on the economic and environmental situation in the country, leading to a number of social problems. Characterizing the development of the EU fertilizer market before the full-

scale invasion of Ukrainian lands by Russian troops and during the period of martial law in Ukraine, it is worth noting the qualitative difference between these two periods. This difference depends on which countries are the largest exporters of fertilizers to the EU.

Based on the statistics of Fertilizers Europe, Eurostat and the European Commission, it can be determined that in 2019-2021, the EU imported 26 million tons of fertilizers worth €6.672 million on average per year. These were mainly nitrogen fertilizers (i.e. 10.4 tons of ammonia, urea, UAN, ammonium nitrate, etc.), phosphate fertilizers (7 million tons) and compound fertilizers containing three nutrients - nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) (approximately 5.6 million tons). The main exporters to the EU fertilizer market were the Russian Federation, Morocco, Egypt, Belarus, Israel, the United Kingdom, and Algeria [1]. Thus, in 2021, the largest exporters of fertilizers to the EU were the Russian Federation - worth €1.785 billion, Morocco and Egypt - worth €675 million and €732 million, and the Republic of Belarus - worth €459 million [3].

Ukraine's role as a fertilizer supplier to the EU market was not significant until February 2022. According to the State Statistics Service, in 2020, Ukrainian producers exported fertilizers to the EU worth USD 76 thousand. US DOLLARS. In 2021, this amount increased by more than 300% and amounted to 2,629 thousand dollars. USD [4, p. 15]. At the same time, these are still meager figures compared to our northeastern neighbors. The key factor that affects this is the lack of access to cheap natural gas, which is available in the Republic of Belarus or the Russian Federation.

Based on analytical studies by Ukrainian scientists, it can be argued that the bulk of Ukrainian fertilizer exports are ammonia and nitrogen fertilizers, with only a small share of complex fertilizers. For example, in 2020, these figures were as follows: ammonia - 48%, nitrogen fertilizers - 52%, and complex fertilizers - 0.5%. Among ammonia and nitrogen fertilizers, urea accounted for 53% and ammonium nitrate for 46% [5, p. 24].

Given that sanctions have been imposed on fertilizer exports from Russian and Belarusian companies to the EU since the outbreak of a full-scale war in February 2022, it can be concluded that other market players will have to take their place. These may be companies within the EU or third countries, including Ukraine.

Analyzing the production of fertilizers by EU producers, it should be noted that the EU has long been subject to the Emissions trading system (hereinafter - ETS) rules. According to EU law, the ETS rules are a scheme

for trading greenhouse gas emission permits within the Community to help reduce greenhouse gas emissions in a cost-effective manner [1]. They are enshrined in Directive 2003/87 of the European Parliament and of the Council “Establishing a scheme for the trading of greenhouse gas emission permits within the Community and amending Council Directive 96/61/EC” and have been further supplemented by other EU regulations. In fact, the CBAM is a continuation of the ETS, with the main difference being that the ETS is extended to producers from the EU, Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, and the CBAM is implemented for fertilizer exporters outside the scope of the ETS rules.

Based on the above provisions, it should be noted that although CBAM does not apply to EU fertilizer producers, this initiative will be an important factor that may change the situation on the fertilizer market in the current environment. This is due to the fact that EU producers subject to EU legislation, the ETS, and exporters from third countries will now be on a level playing field [6]. In addition, given that these rules for reducing greenhouse gas emissions from production activities have been in force in the EU for a long time, this may indicate that EU enterprises have already adapted to them and modernized. This gives them an advantage over producers from third countries where this mechanism is only being introduced.

Thus, it can be concluded that the EU fertilizer market is changing in the current environment. The greening of production by third-country entities, including Ukraine, in accordance with the CBA is a key factor in ensuring the competitiveness of enterprises within the EU, where ETS rules have long been in place.

Implementation of RED norms into national legislation on environmental safety. Legal regulation of biogas and biomethane, their role in ensuring the greening of fertilizer production.

Article 50 of the Constitution of Ukraine and Article 9 of the Law of Ukraine “On Environmental Protection” of June 25, 1991, enshrine the right of citizens to a safe environment. The said law also sets out in Article 52 the basic environmental requirements for the use of mineral fertilizers and other chemicals that have a significant impact on the state of the atmosphere. Ukraine also has a special Law of Ukraine “On Pesticides and Agrochemicals” of March 2, 1995, aimed at regulating legal relations related to state registration, production, trade and safe use of pesticides and agrochemicals for human health and the environment [7].

Today the norms of European legislation related to CBAM and the corresponding greening of production have not been fully implemented in the national legal system. The current regulatory acts in the field of environmental safety, prevention of negative impacts on the ozone layer of the atmosphere and climate are not brought into line with international legal treaties and the EU-Ukraine Association Agreement. An important condition for the adaptation process, according to N.R. Malysheva, is not “blind” copying of EU regulations, but implementation with due regard for the peculiarities of domestic legislation [8, p. 228].

At the same time, the first steps were already taken on December 12, 2019, when the Law of Ukraine “On the Principles of Monitoring, Reporting and Verification of Greenhouse Gas Emissions” was adopted and entered into force in January 2020. More recently, on September 20, 2022, the Law of Ukraine “On the National Register of Pollutant Emissions and Transfers” was adopted. Their importance lies in the introduction of: a system of accounting, monitoring, reporting and verification that will help to obtain accurate information on greenhouse gas emissions from production facilities, ensure control over emissions and processes of their limitation; a mandatory methodology for calculating greenhouse gas emissions for all facilities from which these emissions are made. These regulations have become important tools for ensuring environmental safety during production and other fertilizer management operations. The next legal document adopted by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine is the Resolution of March 21, 2021 “On the establishment of a working group to agree on an approach to applying the border carbon adjustment mechanism to Ukraine for consultations with the European Commission”. The activities of this commission are currently unknown, and therefore it is impossible to assess its effectiveness.

On April 11, 2023, President of Ukraine Volodymyr Zelenskyy signed the Law of Ukraine on the Establishment of the State Fund for Decarbonization and Energy Efficient Transformation. It is also worth noting that the main legislative source of regulation in the field of preventing negative climate change is the Law of Ukraine “On Ratification of the Paris Agreement” of July 14, 2016 [7]. At the same time, the current climate legislation is not sufficient to reduce carbon dioxide emissions and ensure environmental safety, comprehensive greening of production facilities and processes in fertilizer production. In addition, the legislation on pesticides and agrochemicals does not fully establish a legal mechanism for regulat-

ing emissions from production activities of business entities. This demonstrates the importance of optimizing legislation in this area.

According to the author, the main problem of regulatory and legal regulation in the field of CO₂ emissions during production activities is that the legislative norms are aimed at not exceeding the amount of permissible emissions, and not at encouraging enterprises to switch to more environmentally friendly production. In view of this, it can be stated that the main goal of the strategy should be to change the paradigm concerning environmental safety of production in all areas, to form an “environmental culture of life safety” [9, p. 117], including in the management of emissions into the atmosphere by business entities.

Thus, the state should create a strategy whose main goal will be to encourage enterprises to reduce emissions from their production activities and create effective mechanisms for production control and environmental management. This should take into account numerous changes in the norms of the current environmental, trade, and tax legislation, as well as the prospects for the development of new laws and regulations. The main elements of these mechanisms are a new system of quotas and exemptions for environmental taxation, in particular for emissions, with an emphasis on the ETS. This will give an advantage to producers who switch to environmentally friendly production.

The issue of creating a new taxation mechanism is indeed one of the key ones. For example, as of April 2023, according to Article 243.4 of the Tax Code of Ukraine, the tax per 1 ton of CO₂ emissions is UAH 30 [7]. These figures are much lower compared to EU countries, where the tax has reached EUR 60 per ton of emissions in recent years. According to the system proposed by the author, the amount of taxation should increase every year, gradually aligning with the average European amount.

In addition to the above mechanisms, an important component of ensuring environmental safety of production is the development of a network of alternative energy sources. In the author's opinion, this issue requires a separate detailed study, but it should be noted that one of the ways to reduce emissions is to switch to biogas and biomethane as energy sources. The development of these types of alternative energy sources in the EU is increasing every year. Thus, the total production of biogas and biomethane in 2021 amounted to 18.4 billion cubic meters. This accounts for 4.5% of the European Union's gas consumption in 2021. In addition, there were 1067 biomethane plants in Europe in 2021, which is 187 more

than in 2020. As of September 2022, this number increased by another 155 units [10]. Thus, from the above data, we can conclude that the role of alternative energy sources for production in the EU is becoming increasingly important, and EU legislation contributes to this development.

At the same time, it is worth noting that this type of alternative energy source is gradually spreading in Ukraine and is being enshrined in law. For example, the recent amendments to the Law of Ukraine “On Pesticides and Agrochemicals” introduced the concept of “digestate” as residues of raw materials, by-products and waste of animal or vegetable origin, mixed or not, resulting from a controlled anaerobic digestion process with biogas production [7]. It is important to note that this is not the only regulation governing the production of such types of energy, and therefore the new environmental strategy should include further development of the implementation of EU legislation in this area, improvement of legislation and mechanisms for its implementation, and facilitation of the process of transition of enterprises to alternative energy sources in the production of fertilizers.

Thus, it can be concluded that, according to statistics, before the start of Russia’s full-scale military aggression, Ukraine was not an important player in the EU fertilizer export market. At the same time, the greening of fertilizer production and the implementation of the CBAM provisions as a key factor in the development of this sector of the economy can change this situation for the better. In the author’s opinion, Ukraine needs to develop a new environmental strategy that should include two areas.

The first of them will concern improving the legal regulation of CO₂ emissions. Its main elements are: changing the tax rate on CO₂ emissions per ton with a gradual reaching the European average, introducing quotas and tax benefits for enterprises that modernize fertilizer production in accordance with the environmental strategy; implementing the provisions of the CBAM into the national environmental and trade legislation with a procedure for amending existing regulations; developing new bylaws related to fertilizer production and emissions from this activity; changing the amount of sanctions for violation of environmental legislation on CO₂ emissions - using the experience of EU countries.

The second direction of this strategy is related to the legal regulation of biogas/biomethane production, which includes creation of quotas and taxation benefits for enterprises that switch to biogas/biomethane as an alternative energy source; implementation of the EU Regulations and Di-

rectives regulating biogas/biomethane production into national legislation with further development of new regulations and possible codification in the future; creation of state targeted programs to support biogas/biomethane producers.

It is worth noting that to date, namely in April 2023, the first biomethane plant in Ukraine, Gals Agro, was commissioned, and its activities are based on the provisions of the CBA. This means that Ukraine has already started implementing this mechanism and will continue to do so.

Conclusion

Ukraine's implementation of a new environmental strategy to reduce emissions, greening of fertilizer production and transition to alternative energy sources by business entities are key factors in ensuring environmental safety in the fertilizer production sector, as well as increasing the competitiveness of our country as an exporter of fertilizers in the EU market. It is important to develop appropriate legal and enforcement mechanisms for its implementation against the background of the creation of the Border Carbon Adjustment Mechanism and overcoming the consequences of Russian aggression in our country.

The implementation of the European Green Deal, CBAM and the corresponding greening of production can change Ukraine's current position as an exporter of fertilizers to the EU.

The main challenge in this area is the implementation of European environmental legislation into the national legal system, as exemplified by the CBAM. This imposes a number of responsibilities on public authorities and management bodies to improve the environmental and legal mechanisms proposed in the Constitution of Ukraine, the Law of Ukraine "On Environmental Protection", sectoral environmental, trade, tax, administrative, and other legislation.

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